

PROPOSED NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE DESIGN FOR BARANGAY MACAPAGAL VILLAGE HALL

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ABSTRACT

Local government units in the Philippines increasingly depend on digital systems to carry out administrative functions and deliver public services, yet many barangay offices continue to operate on unstructured and unsecured network environments. This study developed a proposed Network Infrastructure Design for Barangay Macapagal Village Hall in Mabalacat City, Pampanga to address persistent issues of unstable internet connectivity, inadequate wireless coverage, and the absence of network segmentation and security mechanisms. Using a descriptive-developmental research design, the proposed infrastructure was built and evaluated through simulation in Cisco Packet Tracer. The design implements VLAN segmentation across five network segments — administrative, SK Office, Health Center, public wireless, and CCTV surveillance — supported by DHCP, NAT, Access Control Lists, firewall configurations, and strategically deployed dual-band wireless access points. Simulation testing confirmed successful network segmentation, automated IP management, controlled inter-VLAN access, stable wireless connectivity, and isolated CCTV operations. The proposed infrastructure addresses the institution's operational requirements and provides a scalable foundation for future ICT expansion. Furthermore, the study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, specifically SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions)

Keywords: *network infrastructure design, VLAN segmentation, Cisco Packet Tracer, network security, local government unit, barangay, wireless connectivity*

INTRODUCTION

Local government units in the Philippines increasingly depend on digital systems to process administrative transactions, manage public records, and coordinate community services. However, many barangay offices continue to operate on basic, unstructured network environments that are insufficient to support these growing digital demands. At Barangay Macapagal Village Hall in Mabalacat City, Pampanga, the existing network infrastructure operates within a single shared connection where administrative computers, wireless users, and monitoring devices compete for the same network resources. This flat, unsegmented topology results in persistent congestion, unstable connectivity, inadequate wireless coverage across operational areas, and critical security

vulnerabilities that expose sensitive administrative data to unauthorized access.

Research has consistently established that unmanaged, single-domain network architectures are a primary source of operational inefficiency in public institutions, particularly as device density and internet dependency increase (Huawei Technologies, 2023). A Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) addresses this by logically grouping devices into separate broadcast domains regardless of their physical location, allowing administrators to isolate traffic without requiring additional physical infrastructure (GeeksforGeeks, n.d.). Studies on VLAN implementation in government and organizational environments have demonstrated that logical network segmentation significantly reduces broadcast traffic, improves bandwidth utilization, and strengthens inter-departmental communication security (Setiawan, Duskarnaen & Ajie, 2024; Al-Batahari et al., 2023). Furthermore, the integration of Access Control Lists (ACLs) and firewall mechanisms has been validated as an effective approach to restricting unauthorized network access and protecting sensitive institutional resources, with firewalls serving as the primary barrier that filters traffic entering and leaving a network based on predetermined security rules (Pan & Liu, 2022; Cisco, n.d.-a). In the Philippine context, local government units have been identified as particularly vulnerable to network inefficiencies due to limited ICT investment, highlighting the need for cost-efficient, scalable, and structured network solutions tailored to small-scale government environments (DICT, 2023). Beyond infrastructure-level inefficiencies, barangay offices have also been shown to lag in the adoption of digital systems for records management and public service delivery, with manual or partially digitized processes remaining common despite the broader push toward e-governance (Tuladteg & Delmo, 2026; Dela Cerna, 2023).

Despite these established solutions, a notable gap exists in the literature concerning the design and simulation of comprehensive network infrastructure for barangay-level local government units in the Philippines. Most existing studies focus on educational institutions or enterprise environments, leaving the specific operational and security requirements of barangay halls largely unaddressed. Barangay Macapagal, the locale of this study, is one of several barangays in Mabalacat City, Pampanga, that continues

to expand its administrative and community services without a corresponding upgrade in network infrastructure (PhilAtlas, 2025). This study aimed to fill that gap by developing a proposed Network Infrastructure Design for Barangay Macapagal Village Hall using Cisco Packet Tracer as the simulation and validation environment.

The significance of this study lies in its direct institutional and community impact. The proposed infrastructure addresses chronic connectivity and security issues that affect the efficiency of public service delivery, the protection of administrative records, and the reliability of communication systems within the barangay hall. Beyond institutional benefits, the study contributes to the Philippines' ongoing digital transformation agenda for local government units and supports the attainment of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals — particularly SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). The study was strictly delimited to a simulated design environment using Cisco Packet Tracer and did not include actual physical deployment or live traffic measurement.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

As illustrated in Figure 1, the study was guided by an Enhanced of the Cisco PPDIIO Methodology. The framework begins with the Input phase, which encompasses the assessment of the existing network conditions, identified operational problems, user requirements, and findings from the review of related literature. The Process phase follows the six sequential stages of the PPDIIO methodology: Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize. These stages guided the researchers in assessing the existing environment, developing the proposed network architecture, simulating and validating the design using Cisco Packet Tracer, evaluating network performance, and identifying recommendations for improvement. The Output phase represents the final deliverable—a validated proposed network infrastructure design complete with a logical topology, VLAN segmentation plan, IP addressing scheme, security configurations, and

supporting technical documentation intended as a reference for future physical implementation within Barangay Macapagal Village Hall.

METHODS

This study adopted a developmental-descriptive research design. The descriptive phase involved assessing the existing network infrastructure of Barangay Macapagal Village Hall to identify operational deficiencies related to connectivity, security, and network management. The developmental phase focused on designing and proposing an improved network infrastructure to address the identified gaps. The design procedures followed the Cisco PPDIIO (Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize) network lifecycle methodology, which provided a systematic framework for assessing network requirements, developing the proposed network architecture, simulating and validating the design using Cisco Packet Tracer, evaluating network performance, and identifying recommendations for optimization and future implementation (Swari & Agussalim, 2023)

The study was conducted at Barangay Macapagal Village Hall, where the existing network environment supports administrative operations, health services, youth office activities, public internet access within the covered court, and CCTV surveillance. Data were gathered through a structured process consisting of coordination, direct observation, site inspection, and semi-structured interviews. The researchers coordinated with the Barangay Captain, Roy Crisanto Castillo, to secure formal permission to conduct the study and obtain information regarding the current network setup. A semi-structured interview and site assessment revealed that the barangay operated on a flat, unsegmented network without centralized management, logical separation of devices, or organized allocation of network resources.

The assessment identified several critical deficiencies in the existing infrastructure. First, the absence of Virtual Local Area Networks (VLANs) resulted in all devices sharing the same broadcast domain, increasing the risk of unauthorized access and unnecessary network traffic. Second, the lack of centralized network management limited the capability to monitor and control connected devices effectively. Third, the existing setup had inadequate security controls and lacked mechanisms for regulating traffic between functional areas. Lastly, the network design did not adequately support future expansion and increasing operational demands.

The design process followed a structured approach consisting of: (1) assessment of existing network requirements; (2) development of a segmented network architecture through VLAN implementation; (3) IP addressing and Router-on-a-Stick configuration for inter-VLAN routing; (4) integration of Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP) for automated IP address

allocation; (5) implementation of Network Address Translation (NAT), Access Control Lists (ACLs), and firewall policies to strengthen security; (6) deployment planning for wireless access points and CCTV surveillance integration; and (7) simulation and validation of the proposed infrastructure using Cisco Packet Tracer.

Cisco Packet Tracer was utilized to simulate the logical topology and validate the functionality of the proposed network. The simulation included the configuration and testing of VLAN segmentation, inter-VLAN routing, DHCP services, NAT operation, ACL enforcement, wireless connectivity, CCTV network isolation, and DNS/HTTP services. The proposed networking devices consisted of a MikroTik hEX RB750Gr3 router, a TP-Link TL-SG2218 managed switch, four TP-Link EAP225 wireless access points, a dedicated HTTP/DNS server, Cat6 Ethernet cabling, a 24-port patch panel, a 9U wall-mounted cabinet, and an APC Easy UPS 650VA to support organized deployment and backup power protection.

The proposed network design was evaluated by certified IT professionals using a customized evaluation instrument based on recognized network design and security principles. The instrument assessed twelve criteria, namely: Network Architecture and Design, Security Architecture and Controls, Compliance and Standards Alignment, Risk Management, Implementation Feasibility, Resources and Cost Planning, Technology and Compatibility, Operational Planning, Performance and Capacity Planning, Documentation Quality and Completeness, Governance and Review Readiness, and Validation and Expert Review Criteria. A four-point Likert scale (4 = Strongly Agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = Disagree, and 1 = Strongly Disagree) was employed to obtain definitive expert judgments by eliminating a neutral midpoint (Jebb et al., 2021).

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically the weighted mean, computed using the formula $\bar{x} = \sum fx/N$, where f represents the frequency of responses, x denotes the scale value, and N represents the total number of responses. Statistical processing was performed using Jamovi software. Mean score interpretations were based on equal interval distribution, computed by dividing the difference between the highest and lowest scale values by the number of response categories, resulting in an interval width of 0.75. Accordingly, the interpretation ranges were as follows: 3.26–4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.51–3.25 = Agree; 1.76–2.50 = Disagree; and 1.00–1.75 = Strongly Disagree. The treatment of Likert-scale responses as interval data and the assumption of equidistant response categories are supported by contemporary methodological literature (Lionello et al., 2021)

RESULTS

Figure 4

Propose Logical Topology

The proposed logical topology improves network organization, minimizes broadcast traffic, enhances security, and provides better bandwidth management across all areas of the barangay hall. Through VLAN implementation and centralized network control, the proposed design ensures stable communication, easier troubleshooting, improved scalability, efficient management of network resources, and effective monitoring of the CCTV surveillance system.

Figure 5

Physical Topology

Figure 5 illustrates the proposed physical network layout of Barangay Macapagal Village Hall, depicting the centralized main switch, interconnected office devices, wireless access points, and CCTV surveillance system. The layout highlights the implementation of VLANs, DHCP, and ACLs to provide organized, secure, and manageable network operations.

All network services configured within Cisco Packet Tracer were successfully validated during simulation testing. DHCP correctly assigned IP addresses within each VLAN's designated /24 address pool. NAT successfully enabled internal devices to access external internet services. ACL rules effectively blocked unauthorized inter-VLAN communication, specifically preventing Covered

Court public wireless users (VLAN 40) from accessing administrative (VLAN 10), health center (VLAN 30), and CCTV (VLAN 50) resources. Inter-VLAN routing through the Router-on-a-Stick configuration allowed controlled communication between authorized VLANs. DNS name resolution and HTTP service responses functioned correctly within the simulated environment. All four wireless access points provided stable connectivity within their designated coverage areas, and CCTV cameras communicated properly within VLAN 50.

Table 14
Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Network Infrastructure

Category	Mean	Interpretation
Network Architecture & Design	3.00	Agree
Security Architecture & Controls	2.50	Disagree
Compliance & Standards Alignment	3.00	Agree
Risk Management	2.75	Agree
Implementation Feasibility	3.00	Agree
Resources and Cost Planning	3.00	Agree
Technology & Compatibility	3.00	Agree
Operational Planning	3.00	Agree
Performance & Capacity Planning	3.00	Agree
Documentation Quality & Completeness	2.75	Agree
Governance & Review Readiness	3.00	Agree
Validation & Expert Review Criteria	3.00	Agree
Grand Mean	2.92	Agree

Eleven of twelve evaluation criteria received a mean score of 2.75 or higher, all interpreted as "Agree." Network Architecture and Design, Compliance and Standards Alignment, Implementation Feasibility, Resources and Cost Planning, Technology and Compatibility, Operational Planning, Performance and Capacity Planning, Governance and Review Readiness, and Validation and Expert Review Criteria each obtained a mean of 3.00. Risk Management and Documentation Quality and Completeness each received a mean of 2.75.

The only criterion that did not reach the "Agree" threshold was Security Architecture and Controls, which obtained a mean score of 2.50 and was interpreted as "Disagree." Although simulation testing confirmed that the implemented ACLs, firewall configurations, and VLAN restrictions functioned according to the intended design, the evaluators indicated that additional security enhancements are necessary prior to actual deployment. These enhancements may include stronger firewall policies, more granular access restrictions between VLANs, improved wireless authentication mechanisms, and the incorporation of advanced security controls appropriate for a production environment. This finding suggests that while the proposed infrastructure provides a solid foundation for secure network operations, further refinement of the security architecture is recommended to improve its overall robustness and readiness for implementation.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study demonstrate that the adoption of a structured, VLAN-based network architecture substantially improved the network performance and security posture of Barangay Macapagal Village Hall relative to its prior flat, unsegmented configuration. Simulation outcomes obtained through Cisco Packet Tracer indicated that the proposed design effectively resolved the connectivity deficiencies, traffic congestion, and security vulnerabilities identified during the preliminary assessment of the barangay's network environment.

A central concern addressed by this study was the absence of network segmentation in the existing infrastructure, wherein administrative workstations, wireless clients, and CCTV devices operated within a single, undifferentiated network domain. The implementation of five VLANs—designated for the Barangay Hall (VLAN 10), SK Office (VLAN 20), Health Center (VLAN 30), Covered Court wireless network (VLAN 40), and CCTV surveillance system (VLAN 50)—established distinct logical boundaries between these operational domains. This configuration is consistent with established practices in VLAN-based government network design, wherein logical segmentation is employed to mitigate internal security risks and restrict unauthorized inter-departmental access (Armando & Widiyari, 2025). The supplementary deployment of Access Control Lists (ACLs) and firewall rules further constrained inter-VLAN communication to explicitly authorized traffic, thereby preventing users connected to the Covered Court's public wireless network from accessing administrative records, health center data, or surveillance feeds.

With respect to connectivity, the integration of router-based services—namely Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), Network Address Translation (NAT), and inter-VLAN routing—addressed the inconsistent IP address management and communication failures that had previously hindered daily barangay operations. DHCP enabled automated address allocation across all five VLANs, while NAT permitted devices within each segment to access external network resources through a shared

public-facing connection. Inter-VLAN routing, configured at the centralized router and managed switch, preserved controlled communication between authorized departments such as the SK Office and Health Center without undermining the segmentation established between VLANs. The strategic placement of dual-band (2.4 GHz and 5 GHz) wireless access points additionally addressed the weak signal coverage previously reported in the SK Office, Health Center, and Covered Court, thereby improving connectivity for administrative functions, community programs, and live broadcast activities—an outcome consistent with national efforts to expand reliable broadband access to underserved local government facilities (Serafica et al., 2023). Reliable connectivity at this level also supports the broader digitalization of barangay record-keeping and service delivery, which similar studies have identified as a prerequisite for effective open-data and geo-based information systems at the barangay level (Mercurio & Hernandez, 2022).

A notable contribution of the proposed design is the establishment of a dedicated CCTV surveillance VLAN. This configuration enhances the barangay's monitoring capability while ensuring that surveillance traffic remains isolated from administrative and public network segments. Such separation between monitoring infrastructure and general network traffic is consistent with recommendations for maintaining the integrity and availability of security systems under conditions of high network utilization (Cisco, n.d.-b), and reflects broader campus-network design guidance that recommends dedicating separate VLANs to security and surveillance traffic to prevent contention with primary business operations (Cisco, 2022).

A limitation of this study is that the reported outcomes were derived exclusively from a simulated environment using Cisco Packet Tracer. Although the simulation confirmed that VLAN segmentation, routing configurations, ACL enforcement, and CCTV integration functioned as designed, real-world deployment may introduce factors that cannot be fully replicated in a virtual environment, including physical signal interference, cable degradation, hardware constraints, and actual traffic loads during peak operational hours. Future research should therefore prioritize the physical implementation of the proposed design, ideally under the supervision of a qualified network professional, with subsequent evaluation focused on empirical measures of bandwidth utilization, latency, packet loss, and wireless signal performance under live operating conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

This study established that the proposed Network Infrastructure Plan for Barangay Macapagal Village Hall constitutes a viable and structured solution to the operational network challenges identified at the site, achieving its general objective through comprehensive technical assessment, architectural design, and expert validation.

The proposed architecture has the potential to address the critical network gaps identified in the existing setup. Through VLAN segmentation, DHCP, NAT, ACLs, firewall configurations, inter-VLAN routing, and strategically deployed wireless access points, the design offers a structured approach to improving network organization, connectivity, and security within Barangay Macapagal Village Hall. While the findings were derived from a simulated environment using Cisco Packet Tracer, the results indicate that the proposed infrastructure may serve as a practical reference for future physical implementation and further real-world evaluation.

The blueprint is highly appropriate for the operational landscape of Barangay Macapagal Village Hall. The five-VLAN architecture—comprising VLAN 10 (Barangay Hall), VLAN 20 (SK Office), VLAN 30 (Health Center), VLAN 40 (Covered Court Wireless Network), and VLAN 50 (CCTV Surveillance Network)—directly answers the multi-area layout of the barangay facility, replacing an undifferentiated shared network with structured, logically isolated segments. The design achieves security through ACL and firewall enforcement that programmatically restricts unauthorized access between departments, particularly preventing free Wi-Fi users from reaching administrative, health, and surveillance resources; connectivity through centralized routing and access-port/trunk-port configuration on the managed switch; coverage through strategically placed 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz access points; and resource efficiency through a design that builds upon existing equipment rather than requiring a full hardware replacement, enabling phased implementation as funding becomes available.

With an expert validation rating of "Agree" (2.92 overall weighted mean), this network infrastructure plan stands as a technically sound, simulation-validated design that successfully modernizes Barangay Macapagal Village Hall into a more organized, secure, and operationally reliable local government facility. While the evaluation identified Security Architecture and Controls as an area for further refinement—particularly stronger firewall configurations, more granular VLAN access restrictions, and enhanced wireless security protocols—the overall results affirm that the proposed design is feasible, scalable, and making it a practical reference for future implementation subject to real-world validation., offering a replicable framework for similar Philippine barangay offices facing comparable network deficiencies.

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